

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Benzaldehydes by Quinolinium Chlorochromate

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Manuscript received 28 November 1997, accepted 23 March 1998

The kinetics of oxidation of benzaldehyde (BA) and several *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzaldehydes to the corresponding benzoic acids by quinolinium chlorochromate (QCC) have been studied. The reaction is first order each in [QCC], [substrate] and $[H^+]$. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters calculated. The rate decreases with an increase in the amount of acetic acid in its aqueous mixture. Addition of acrylonitrile induces polymerization. The rates of the reactions have been analysed in terms of Taft's dual substituent parameter equation. Suitable mechanism has been proposed.

A number of reports on the mechanism of oxidation of several substrates by halochromates of nitrogen containing heterocyclic cationic compounds are available¹. Quinolinium chlorochromate (QCC) is shown to oxidize a variety of alcohols to yield the carbonyl compounds². The carbonyl compounds are found to be further oxidized with QCC and there is no work about the mechanism of the reaction. The present communication reports the kinetics of oxidation of substituted benzaldehydes by QCC and evaluates the reaction constant. Mechanistic aspects are also discussed.

Results and Discussion

Aromatic aldehydes being in large excess, plots of $\log [QCC]$ vs time are linear, indicating a first order dependence on [QCC]. But the first order rate constant (k_1) decreases as [QCC] increases. The plots of [QCC] vs $1/k_1$ is linear with unit slope. Such observations have been reported by several authors³. This may be due to the faster rate of formation of the QCC-ester as the intermediate compared to the rate of ester decomposition. The rate increases steadily with increase in [BA]. A plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [BA]$ is linear with a slope of 1.03 ± 0.006 ($r = 0.999$) passing through the origin. These observations lead to the conclusion that the order in [BA] is unity (Table 1).

The increase in $[H^+]$ increases the reaction rate and shows a direct first order dependence on $[H^+]$ (Table 2). The rate of oxidation is unaffected by varying the ionic strength with the addition of $NaClO_4$ (Table 2). Increase in the percentage of acetic acid in the solvent mixture decreases the rate and a positive slope is obtained for the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/D$ (Table 3).

The radical formation has been tested with acrylonitrile when a polymer precipitated in methanol under deaerated condition. This has been confirmed by a single derivative curve obtained in the esr spectrum. Such observation has

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON REACTION RATES AT 303 K IN ACID MEDIA

[HClO ₄] = 1.0 mol dm ⁻³ , μ = 1.2 mol dm ⁻³ , HOAc-H ₂ O : 50% (v/v)			
10 ² [BA] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ [QCC] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k_1 s ⁻¹	10 ³ k_2 dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1.5	1.0	5.96	3.97
2.0	1.0	7.72	3.86
3.0	1.0	12.2	4.07
4.0	1.0	15.7	3.93
5.0	1.0	19.8	3.96
6.0	1.0	23.8	3.97
4.0	2.0	15.3	3.58
4.0	3.0	12.7	3.18
4.0	4.0	10.9	2.73
4.0	5.0	8.20	2.05
4.0	6.0	6.40	1.60

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING $[H^+]$ AND $[ClO_4^-]$ ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION AT 303 K

[BA] = 4.0×10^{-2} mol dm ⁻³ , [QCC] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm ⁻³ , HOAc-H ₂ O : 50% (v/v)		
[HClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	[NaClO ₄] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k_1 s ⁻¹
0.2	1.2	2.69
0.4	1.2	6.01
0.6	1.2	9.72
0.8	1.2	13.4
1.0	1.2	15.9
1.0	1.1	15.7
1.0	1.3	15.3
1.0	1.4	15.8
1.0	1.5	15.5
1.0	1.6	15.9

already been reported in the oxidation of aldehydes⁴.

Mechanism and rate law : Based on the present experimental observations and from the reports of previous

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING PERCENTAGE OF SOLVENT ON THE RATE OF OXIDATION AT 303 K

[BA] = 4.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [QCC] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, $\mu = 1.2$ mol dm⁻³

% HOAc	D	10 ⁵ k ₁ s ⁻¹
30	72.0	11.8
40	63.3	13.5
50	56.0	15.7
60	45.5	21.1
70	38.5	27.2

work with chromic acid oxidations⁵, an initial two-electron transfer with the formation of chromium(IV) has been formulated. Cr^{IV} reacts with an aldehyde molecule to form an aryl radical and Cr^{III}. The aryl radical reduces QCC to Cr^V which further reacts with another aldehyde molecule by a two-electron transfer to form Cr^{III}. The involvement of the intermediate valence states of chromium in the reaction has been tested with the induced oxidation by Mn^{II}. The reaction rate is found to decrease to one-third as in the case of chromic acid oxidation of aldehydes⁶.

Benzaldehyde and its substituted members are not hydrated to any appreciable extent in aqueous acetic acid medium⁷. No reaction is known in which the nucleophilic attack on tetrahedral carbon of aldehyde hydrate is faster than that on free aldehyde⁸. So it is fair to assume that the free CHO group of the substrate is the reactive species. The reaction proceeds with the formation of a QCC-ester as the intermediate (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Water molecule abstracts the proton from the ester in the rate-limiting step. This is supported by the observed linear correlation between the logarithm of rate constant and the pH⁹. The positive reaction constant accounts for the loss of aldehydic hydrogen atom as a proton⁵.

Since the rate of the reaction is the decomposition of the QCC-ester, the rate law is given as

$$\text{Rate} = k_1[\text{QCC} - \text{ester}] \quad (7)$$

or

$$\text{Rate} = K_1 K_2 k_1 [\text{aldehyde}][\text{QCC}][\text{H}^+] \quad (8)$$

where, $K_1 = k_3/k_{-3}$ and $K_2 = k_4/k_{-4}$.

Effect of substituents: Effect of substituents on the rate of oxidation has been studied with a number of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzaldehydes. In general, the rate of reaction is accelerated by electron-withdrawing substituents and retarded by electron-releasing ones (Table 4). A plot of $\log(k_2/k_2^0)$ vs σ gives a positive slope with ρ value as +1.39 ($r = 0.957$). Since the reaction rates failed to show a significant correlation with any single-parameter substituent constants, the rates have been analysed in terms of the dual substituent parameter equation of Taft¹⁰,

$$\log k_2 = \log k_2^0 + \sigma_1 \rho_1 + \sigma_R \rho_R \quad (9)$$

The rates of oxidation of *para*- and *meta*-substituted benzaldehydes have been separately correlated with σ_1 and one of the four σ_R values, viz. σ_R^o , $\sigma_R(\text{BA})$, σ_R^+ and σ_R^- . The results are summarized in Table 5. The significance of correlation has been tested by means of an 'F' test. The values of conjugation effect λ^p (1.00 to 1.63) show that the resonance effect is the predominant electronic effect for the *para*-substituents and the field effect is the dominating one for the *meta*-substituents ($\sigma^m = 0.17$ to 0.40). The coefficient of multiple correlation (R), the standard deviation (SD), f and t tests are used as the criteria of goodness of fit.

Activation parameters: The activation parameters have been computed from a plot of $\log k_2$ vs $1/T$ in the temperature range 303–333 K (Table 4). The activation enthalpies and entropies are linearly related by the equation¹¹,

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0 + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger \quad (10)$$

where β is the isokinetic temperature and ΔH_0 the enthalpy of activation when $\Delta S^\ddagger = 0$ and usually has no physical significance. The isokinetic temperature obtained from the slope is 432 K ($r = 0.997$). This linear correlation indicates that a single mechanism is operating throughout the series¹². This is further confirmed with the Exner plot¹³. When rate measurements at two different temperatures have been made, the experimental data can be treated by the equation,

$$\log k_2(T_2) = a + b \log k_2(T_1) \quad (11)$$

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE EFFECT AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF QCC OXIDATION OF BENZALDEHYDES

Substrate	$10^3 k_2, \text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$				ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger
	303 K	313 K	323 K	333 K	(± 0.2) kJ mol ⁻¹	(± 1.0) J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	(± 2.5) kJ mol ⁻¹
BA	3.96	6.47	10.3	16.8	37.7	166	90.5
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	0.59	1.25	2.29	4.55	53.9	129	94.9
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	1.45	2.57	4.35	7.79	44.1	154	93.1
<i>p</i> -COOC ₂ H ₅	9.33	13.8	20.5	30.8	30.8	182	88.7
<i>p</i> -CN	18.3	25.3	35.8	50.1	25.6	194	87.3
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	24.5	33.9	45.0	62.2	23.2	199	86.5
<i>p</i> -F	2.27	3.96	6.69	10.8	41.1	160	92.0
<i>p</i> -Cl	5.15	7.98	12.4	18.6	33.4	179	90.3
<i>p</i> -Br	5.66	8.79	13.5	20.8	33.7	177	90.0
<i>p</i> -I	6.68	10.2	15.9	23.6	32.9	178	89.5
<i>m</i> -CH ₃	2.86	4.85	7.71	13.7	41.0	159	91.6
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	4.76	7.59	12.3	20.5	38.2	164	90.4
<i>m</i> -Cl	6.59	10.1	14.8	21.8	30.7	186	89.8
<i>m</i> -Br	7.42	11.2	16.4	25.2	31.4	182	89.3
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	14.3	20.7	28.6	42.1	27.3	190	87.7

 TABLE 5—CORRELATION OF RATES OF OXIDATION OF *para*- AND *meta*-SUBSTITUTED BENZALDEHYDES BY QCC WITH SUBSTITUENT PARAMETERS AT 303 K

Substituent constants	ρ_1	ρ_R	R	SD	λ	f	F	t
<i>para</i> -Substituted								
σ_1, σ_R^0	1.10	1.79	0.9869	0.30	1.63	0.08	55.4	9.20
σ_1, σ_R^+	1.06	1.06	0.9903	0.26	1.00	0.03	77.0	23.1
σ_1, σ_R^-	0.98	1.12	0.9808	0.28	1.14	0.08	62.3	10.2
$\sigma_1, \sigma_R^{(BA)}$	1.13	1.52	0.9778	0.29	1.35	0.05	60.45	9.40
<i>meta</i> -Substituted								
σ_1, σ_R^0	0.82	0.32	0.9876	0.25	0.39	0.04	8.14	18.6
σ_1, σ_R^+	0.82	0.14	0.9748	0.26	0.17	0.07	7.62	15.9
σ_1, σ_R^-	0.76	0.23	0.9979	0.22	0.30	0.03	12.3	15.9
$\sigma_1, \sigma_R^{(BA)}$	0.82	0.23	0.9650	0.26	0.28	0.06	7.71	17.2

$f = \text{SD}/\text{root mean square of } \log(k_2/k_2^0); \lambda = \rho_R/\sigma_1$

where, $k_2(T_2)$ and $k_2(T_1)$ are the rate constants at temperatures T_2 and T_1 ($T_2 > T_1$) respectively. Applying this equation, a better correlation is obtained ($r = 0.998$) when $\log k_2$ (313 K) is plotted against $\log k_2$ (303 K). The isokinetic temperature is found to be 425 K. This serves as an argument that the reactions of all substituted benzaldehydes follow a common mechanism.

Experimental

Quinolinium chlorochromate², *p*-ethoxycarbonyl¹³ and *p*-iodobenzaldehydes¹⁴ were prepared using reported procedures. All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck) and the liquid aldehydes were used after vacuum-distillation. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by maintaining a large excess of the aldehyde over QCC. The solvent was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water mixture. The ionic strength was maintained at 1.2 mol dm⁻³ using NaClO₄ and the acid concentration was 1.0 mol dm⁻³ (HClO₄). The reactions were carried out at constant temperatures (± 0.1 K) and were followed upto 80% completion. The unreacted QCC was estimated iodometrically. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_1) were computed from linear least-squares plot of $\log [\text{QCC}]$ vs time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant was obtained by the relation, $k_2 = k_1/[\text{substrate}]$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Stoichiometric studies showed that 3 moles of aldehyde consumed 2 moles of QCC in accordance with equation (12) to give the corresponding carboxylic acid,

Benzaldehyde (0.2 mol) and QCC (0.4 mol) were mixed together with perchloric acid (1.0 mol) in 50% (v/v) aqueous-acetic acid (total volume 100 ml). The reaction mixture was set aside for about 24 h to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then vacuum-evaporated and extracted with ether. The ether layer was separated and dried. The residue was confirmed as benzoic acid by the m.m.p., tlc and spectral analysis. The percentage yield was calculated to be 95%.

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